

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Hassan**FIRST NAME:** Usamah**PROGRAM CODE:** DIFE**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. In the context of academic writing, plagiarism is a critical issue that undermines the integrity of scholarly work. Considering the strategies for avoiding plagiarism, which of the following is NOT a valid strategy for maintaining academic integrity in your writing?

- Citing all sources, including paraphrased content, to acknowledge the original authors.
- Utilizing plagiarism detection software to review your work before submission.
- Relying on a significant amount of common knowledge without citation, assuming it does not require acknowledgment.¹**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck & Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, fourth edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

- Incorporating quotes accurately and providing a clear distinction between one's own thoughts and the sourced information.
2. Focusing on the application of the Chicago Style in both academic and professional writings, why is the Chicago Style particularly valued in scholarly publications?
- Its exclusive use of in-text citations enhances the readability of academic texts.
- The flexibility in choosing between the author-date system and the notes-bibliography system caters to diverse disciplinary needs.²**
- Its preference for endnotes over footnotes simplifies the page layout.
- The style's insistence on using the serial comma ensures precision in complex lists.
3. In the context of ensuring the integrity of scholarly work, the "Turabian Rule of Style" emphasizes the importance of citation accuracy. According to the guide, which of the following practices is NOT recommended for maintaining citation integrity?
- Regularly using citation management tools to organize and format references.
- Double-checking all citations against original sources for accuracy before submission.
- Relying solely on automated citation generators without reviewing for errors.³**
- Keeping multiple backups of your citation library to safeguard against data loss.

² Ibid., 43–57.

³ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 145–146.

4. The Turabian Rule of Style outlines detailed guidelines for using the Notes-Bibliography citation style. Which of the following elements is INCORRECTLY paired with its guideline?

- Footnotes should begin on the page where they are referenced.
- The use of "ibid." is encouraged for consecutive citations from the same source.⁴**
- Bibliographies should list sources in alphabetical order by the author's last name.
- Notes can be formatted as either footnotes at the bottom of the page or endnotes at the end of the document.

5. The Turabian Rule of Style dedicates a section to the prevention of plagiarism, emphasizing responsible academic writing. According to the guide, which of the following is NOT listed as a method to avoid plagiarism?

- Incorporating quotations into your text with clear attribution to the original author.
- Paraphrasing is a primary method for integrating source material into your writing.
- Ensuring all sources, regardless of whether they are directly quoted or paraphrased, are cited.
- Limiting the review of sources relevant to your research to minimize accidental plagiarism.⁵**

⁴ Ibid., 167.

⁵ Ibid., 370–380.

6. "A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research" emphasizes the potential integration of quantitative and qualitative methods within dissertation research. According to the guide, which statement best reflects the author's stance on mixing these methodologies?
- Quantitative and qualitative methods are fundamentally incompatible, advocating for a strict adherence to one methodology per research project.
 - The integration of quantitative and qualitative methods is discouraged unless a clear rationale is provided in the dissertation's methodology chapter.
 - The guide endorses a mixed-methods approach, asserting that quantitative and qualitative methodologies can complement each other and enhance the research's depth and breadth.⁶**
 - Quantitative methods are regarded as superior, with qualitative methods only recommended for exploratory phases or when quantitative data is unobtainable.
7. In the context of minimizing researcher bias, "A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research" offers several strategies. Which of the following is NOT mentioned as a method to counteract bias in dissertation research?
- Maintaining a transparent relationship between the researcher's biases and the research process.

⁶ James P. Sampson, *Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 7.

- Using a double-blind procedure to ensure the researcher's biases do not influence the study's outcomes.⁷**
 - Clearly describing potential biases to allow readers to assess their impact on the research findings.
 - Engaging in reflexivity to critically examine how the researcher's assumptions may influence the study.
8. According to "Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation," ensuring methodological alignment is critical throughout the dissertation process. Which of the following is NOT a component where alignment is crucial for maintaining the integrity of qualitative research?
- Alignment between the research questions and the chosen qualitative methodology.
 - Consistency in the application of theoretical frameworks across different chapters of the dissertation.
 - Ensuring that the literature review directly contradicts the research findings for the sake of argumentative balance.⁸**
 - Coherence between data collection methods and the overarching research questions.

⁷ Ibid., 8–9.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2018), 233–298.

9. Reflecting on the challenges of completing a qualitative dissertation as discussed in "Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation," which of the following is NOT identified as a common obstacle?

- Difficulty in narrowing down a broad research topic into a manageable and researchable question.
- Navigating the iterative, nonlinear process of qualitative research, including revisiting and revising earlier steps based on new insights.
- The requirement for qualitative research to follow a strict linear progression from proposal to completion without deviation⁹.**
- Overcoming feelings of inadequacy and frustration due to the complex and demanding nature of the dissertation process.

10. Reflecting on the challenges of completing a qualitative dissertation as discussed in "Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation," which of the following is NOT identified as a common obstacle?

- Difficulty in narrowing down a broad research topic into a manageable and researchable question.
- Navigating the iterative, nonlinear process of qualitative research, including revisiting and revising earlier steps based on new insights.
- The requirement for qualitative research is to follow a strict linear progression from proposal to completion without deviation.¹⁰**

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ Ibid.

- Overcoming feelings of inadequacy and frustration due to the complex and demanding nature of the dissertation process.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2018.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.